

The Closed-Loop Robotic Glockenspiel: Improving Musical Robots Using Embedded Musical Information Retrieval

Jason Long
New Zealand School of Music
Victoria University of
Wellington
New Zealand
jason.long@ecs.victoria.ac.nz

Ajay Kapur
New Zealand School of Music
Victoria University of
Wellington
New Zealand
ajay@karmetik.com

Dale A. Carnegie
School of Engineering and
Computer Science
Victoria University of
Wellington
New Zealand
dale.carnegie@vuw.ac.nz

ABSTRACT

Musical robots provide artists and musicians with the ability to realise complex new musical ideas in real acoustic space. However, most musical robots are created with open-loop control systems, many of which require time consuming calibration and do not reach the level of reliability of other electronic musical instruments such as synthesizers. This paper outlines the construction of a new robotic musical instrument, the Closed-Loop Robotic Glockenspiel, and discusses the improved robustness, usability and expressive capabilities that closed-loop control systems and embedded musical information retrieval processes can afford robotic musical instruments. The hardware design of the instrument is described along with the firmware of the embedded MIR system. The result is a new desktop robotic musical instrument that is capable of continuous unaided recalibration and latency compensation, is as simple to use as more traditional hardware electronic sound-sources and provides musicians with new expressive capabilities.

Author Keywords

Musical Robotics, Musical Information Retrieval, Control System, Closed Loop, MIDI, Glockenspiel, NIME, MIR, Onset Detection, Latency Compensation

ACM Classification

H.5.5 [Information Interfaces and Presentation] Sound and Music Computing, I.2.9 [Artificial Intelligence] Robotics—Sensors.

1. INTRODUCTION

Musical robotics is a field within music technology that is concerned with actuating real-world acoustic sound-objects with computer control. These systems are capable of facilitating the creation of expressive musical works that combine the benefits of precise control and electronic synchronization with those of real acoustic instruments and spaces. At the present time, there are very few commercial offerings of robotic musical instruments, and most are constructed

by composer-creators in academic or artistic environments. While these one-off instruments generally achieve their purpose of creating new and interesting music, they often require extensive manual calibration, frequent maintenance and lack the reliability and repeatability of commercially produced musical instruments or industrial robots. The following quote from an interview with musical roboticist Meiwa Denki exemplifies this issue:

“The instruments sometimes break, which becomes part of the show. It’s kind of like F1 racing. We try hard to keep them from breaking, but with more than 30 instruments, some kind of trouble always arises” [5]

One of the key elements that makes industrial robots reliable is the use of sensors that provide control systems with continuously polled closed-loop feedback on their position, pressure, temperature or other parameters. In the case of musical robots, though these types of sensing can be useful, the most important outputs are the audible vibrations coming from the sound objects themselves. Therefore in order to effectively close the loop in such systems, audio sensing apparatuses must be used. However, since a straight reading of a sound-pressure wave won’t provide sufficient musical details with which to inform the control system, musical information retrieval (MIR) techniques such as onset detection, loudness analysis and spectral analysis can be used to make sense of the data. With this data feeding back into the control system of a robotic musical instrument, the instrument can continuously refine its performance to match the intended musical intentions of the operator.

2. BACKGROUND

People have created musical automata for millennia. Development has progressed from early water and wind powered sound makers, through programmable organs and carillons to sophisticated reproducing pianos which can expressively reproduce a famous piano performance on command. In the early to mid 20th century some composers such as Conlon Nancarrow and George Antheil utilised the extra-human capabilities of musical automata to realise new, complex compositions that otherwise would have been impossible [15].

In the 1970s, artists such as Trimpin and Godfried Willem Raes began developing a new variety of musical automata, this time under computer control, pioneering the field of musical robotics [6]. In recent decades, as the barrier to entry for artists to create electro-mechanical works has lowered, musical robotic development has accelerated and regular shows are being conducted with large groups of mu-

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sical robots such as the Karmetik Machine Orchestra, Pat Metheny’s Orchestrion and the Logos Robot Orchestra [11].

2.1 Robotic Polyphonic Pitched Percussion

Pitched percussion is an instrument class that is popular with musical roboticists. Unlike the playing of a cello, which requires several different mechanisms operating in conjunction in order to produce a single note, a single-actuator strike on a percussion instrument is able to produce a satisfying output. Examples of robotic pitched percussion include instruments in the Karmetik Machine Orchestra, Eric Singer’s SingerBots, Raes’ Robot Orchestra [11], Ken Caulkins’ works [2] and Trimpin’s Conloninpurple, Circumference and Magnitude in C# installations [4], not to mention the variety of computer controlled pianos in existence.

Some of these instruments use mallets to strike keys from above, while others strike directly from below, allowing human performers to play the instrument simultaneously. However, almost all designs utilise microcontrollers to trigger an array of linear solenoids, which do not exhibit particularly linear characteristics with regards to velocity control [7], and also create varying degrees of latency [9].

2.2 Calibration of Musical Robots

Various methods have been used to attempt to calibrate musical robots in order to make improvements on these shortcomings and deliver more accurate performances of musical works. In order to correctly map the 127 Note-on values available for use in standard MIDI systems to pulse-lengths that drive the solenoids, the value 1 should be mapped to the shortest pulse which reliably strikes the key, the value 127 should be mapped to the longest pulse which stops being applied before the striker makes contact with the key, and the values between these two extremes should ideally adhere to a curve that results in 126 steps of equally increasing loudness as perceived by a human.

Murphy proposes pre-performance automatic calibration systems that seek to improve the accuracy of open-loop solenoid based percussion systems [13]. Similar techniques were also proposed for use with robotic string picking instruments [14]. While these types of pre-performance calibration systems do notably improve the performance of these robotic systems, they add to the complexity of use and time required in their setup by requiring a personal computer to carry out the calibration.

These issues have been addressed by Shawn Trail with his STARI robot, which utilises a single-board BeagleBone computer to embed his PureData based tuning routine inside the robot [20]. Other similar solutions include Trimpin modifying commercial guitar tuners to tune his *If VI Were IX* robotic guitar installation and the automatic tuning pegs of the Gibson Robotic Guitar. However, all of these pre-performance calibration systems leave the instruments vulnerable to any changes in the environment during a performance that may affect the instrument’s response.

2.3 MIR and Musical Robots

Koji Shibuya has published several papers that emphasize the necessity of ‘kansei’ in musical performance. Translated as ‘perception’ or ‘sensibility’, kansei is the ability for a performer to continuously listen to their own musical output and use that information to adjust their actions in real-time in order to bring that output closer to an ideal goal [17]. In order to achieve such functionality with a musical robot, it is necessary to receive an audio feed from the instrument and utilize musical information retrieval (MIR) techniques in order to extract useful information from the signal that can inform the robot’s future actions.

In the last few years some research has been conducted which uses MIR techniques on robotically actuated audio streams. Ness et al. label this area ‘Music Information Robotics’ in their study which utilised a single external microphone to aid in pre-performance calibration and use audio based drum classification to match an array of robotically actuated percussion instruments with their corresponding control channels [16]. Solis et al. performed experiments which used pitch analysis to provide feedback on the performance of their anthropomorphic flute playing robot [18], and Batula et al. used audio and haptic signals to classify their humanoid robots’ strikes as ‘good’ or ‘bad’.

3. THE ROBOTIC GLOCKENSPIEL

The first iteration of the robotic glockenspiel design utilised a simple open loop configuration and is pictured on the top left of Figure 1. The control box pictured on the top right of Figure 1 received MIDI commands via either a panel mounted 5-pin DIN connector or via USB. It then produced higher voltage pulses which were sent to the instrument via a standard DB25 cable in order to control the solenoids mounted under the glockenspiel keys.

The instrument was designed with contemporary music and installation performance in mind and operates with very low levels of extraneous acoustic noise and comparatively low levels of latency, between 10 ms and 25 ms, making it suitable for real-time interactive applications [8].

Figure 1: Top Left: The Robotic Glockenspiel. Top Right: The control box necessary for operating it. Bottom: An exploded rendering showing the inside of the instrument.

However, in performance it was noticed that a straight mapping of MIDI velocities to pulse-widths that was identical for each key resulted in inconsistencies among the keys’ volumes. Though manually editing the firmware of the control box with customized pulse-width ranges for each key provided improvements in that area, it was observed that over time and especially when the instrument is transported between venues, the manually edited values would no longer provide optimum performance.

As a result, the software interface shown in Figure 2 was created in the Reaktor visual programming environment. The plugin allows the user to specify minimum and max-

imum velocities for each note of the robotic glockenspiel, and when inserted into the MIDI stream between the original signal and the instrument, maps the inputted signals between these limits.

Figure 2: The external software interface used to manually calibrate the Robotic Glockenspiel.

This method added convenience when calibrating the instrument, but the manual calibration method was still time consuming, mapping the MIDI velocities to a small range decreased the resolution of the control signal, and since even slight changes occurring during a performance with the instrument can have a significant effect on the velocity response, pre-performance calibration was deemed insufficient. This lack of reliability meant that in order to prevent the missing of notes during very quiet passages due to slightly short pulse-widths being sent, conservative minimum values had to be set, which had a negative effect on the dynamic expressiveness of the instrument's performance. In order to solve these problems it was necessary to implement an embedded closed-loop control system that was capable of continuously monitoring the performance of the instrument and autonomously making adjustments as necessary.

4. THE CLOSED-LOOP UPGRADES

Figure 3: The Closed-Loop Robotic Glockenspiel.

The Closed Loop Robotic Glockenspiel is a complete revamp of the original instrument, designed to deliver improvements in reliability, repeatability, usability and musical expressiveness. To achieve these goals, it was decided remove the control box altogether and integrate all of the electronic hardware inside the instrument itself. One of the key objectives of the instrument's design was to ensure that it was no more complex to operate than a commercial desktop synthesizer. In keeping with this philosophy, the back

panel as shown in Figure 3 contains just power, MIDI, USB, an audio out connector and a volume knob.

4.1 The Mechanics

Each individual key of the glockenspiel is paired with a tubular linear push-type solenoid. Striking the key with the solenoid's bare metal rod produces a fatiguing sound in which the higher harmonics dominate the output. Several different striking materials were trialed, and it was decided that wooden balls provided the most agreeable timbre.

Several configurations were tested in order to pick up the sound from the keys. One popular method as used on the DSRmarimba is attaching piezoelectric discs directly to the keys [19]. Unfortunately with the small, lightweight glockenspiel keys, this method had the effect of dampening their movement and noticeably detuning them. To avoid these pitfalls, a method using magnets and inductors similar to that of the EMvibe was chosen [1].

1 mm thick, 4 mm in diameter neodymium magnets were attached to the keys near their central extremes using Araldite Super Strength glue. Beneath each of these magnets, an electromagnetic coil is positioned close enough to pick up the vibrations of the magnet, but not so close as to inhibit the key's free movement. Since there is no wiring attached to the keys directly, they are able to move freely, and the neodymium magnets have a low enough mass that any potential detuning of the keys is imperceptible. The whole configuration is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: The action of a single key.

4.2 The Electronics

The electronics of the instrument comprise of three main sections, the power supply, the digital circuitry including microcontrollers, and the analogue audio circuits. For this prototype instrument the circuit boards were created via CNC mill, in a through-hole configuration. The three sections are discussed in turn below.

4.2.1 Power

The instrument is powered using a standard IEC cable and toggling the illuminating power switch turns it on. The mains power is routed through an internal fuse and is passed on to the primary winding of a power transformer inside the unit. A toroidal transformer was chosen rather than a typical EI model due to their high power efficiency, low profile, the required low levels of flux-leakage noise due to being mounted in close proximity to analogue audio circuits [12], and low acoustic noise [21]. The mains voltage section of the unit is physically separated from the rest of the internals with a 3D printed barrier for safety.

The toroidal transformer provides dual secondary volt-

Figure 5: The Power Supply (left), Solenoid Control (middle) and Audio Processing (right) circuit boards.

ages of 60 vac for the solenoid supply voltage and 9 vac for the analogue audio and digital circuitry. The power supply circuit board shown on the left of Figure 5 was created which rectifies the solenoid supply voltage to an unregulated 80 v, provides regulated +9 v and -9 v DC for the audio circuits, and +5 v to power the logic circuits.

4.2.2 Digital Control

Both the control logic and DSP algorithms of the prototype are implemented on a pair of Arduino Due microcontroller boards. These boards were chosen due to their convenience for rapid prototyping, array of on-board 12 bit analogue to digital converters and ability to process several channels of audio at a 44.1kHz sample rate.

The unit can receive commands from both the standard MIDI input via the 5-pin DIN connector and via USB. The USB-B socket is mounted to a small PCB running an altered Hiduino firmware on a Atmega16u2 chip [3]. This firmware implements bidirectional MIDI communication between the on-board Due boards and a connected device.

Control signals comprised of short pulses to activate the solenoids are transmitted from the microcontroller boards to the solenoid control board pictured in the middle of Figure 5. This simple board implements the same MOSFET based solenoid control circuit outlined in [10] for each of the 21 keys of the instrument.

4.2.3 Audio Circuitry

The analogue audio processing circuitry is housed on the circuit board shown on the right of Figure 5. The board receives signals from each of the 21 pickup coils positioned under the keys of the instrument and processes their output with op-amp circuits implemented in active filter and variable gain amplifier configurations.

These circuits first low-pass the audio signal with a cut-off frequency of approximately 20kHz in order to remove extraneous noise. PCB-mounted potentiometers are then included in the op-amp feedback path in order to adjust the gain applied to each channel and optimize their signal-to-noise ratio. After amplification, the signal is then high-passed with a cut-off of approximately 10 hz in order to remove DC offset. Finally, the signal is biased to a virtual ground at 1.65 v prior to being sent to the microcontroller boards for analogue to digital conversion.

The output pins of each of the amplifier circuits are also connected to a separate summing amplifier circuit before the biasing stage. The summing amplifier is equipped with an internal trim-pot to set the maximum output voltage of the mix-down, the signal is routed through the panel-mounted volume potentiometer, and is buffered by a final op-amp circuit in a voltage follower configuration before being output

to the 1/4" panel-mounted TS socket.

Figure 6: An exploded render showing the internals of the instrument.

4.3 The Firmware

A single firmware is written to both of the microcontrollers, with a flag which assigns each of the two boards to one of the two groups of solenoids and coils. The firmware serves multiple purposes. Firstly, it manages communications with the outside world via MIDI in and out signals, secondly, it produces the precise pulses used to control the solenoids which strike the keys of the instrument, and thirdly, it implements the onset and amplitude detection algorithms on the audio received from the coils in order to continuously adjust the instrument's performance. The first two functions have been documented thoroughly with regards to other musical robotics systems and will not be discussed here. However the embedded MIR methods will be discussed below.

4.3.1 Onset Detection

Onset detection is a technique utilised in order to determine the point in time when the start of a musical event occurs. Many different algorithms are used and their effectiveness varies greatly depending on the source material.

The process of onset detection in musical robotics is significantly simplified in comparison to general purpose applications due to the fact that several pieces of information that are generally unknown in a human performance are pre-determined in a robotic one. Firstly, the approximate

point in time that an onset is expected to occur is established. This enables the algorithm to ignore any incidental onsets that could be detected outside of a small window of time. Secondly, since the glockenspiel is a percussion instrument, the envelope of each strike consists of a short, sharp attack, and a slow and predictable release. This means that the algorithm need not account for sounds with slow attack times or unpredictable envelopes.

Since the sound pickup method is based around magnetism rather than sound pressure waves, it is not necessary to account for the possibility of unintended acoustic sounds within the proximity of the instrument interfering with the audio feed. Also, because of the fact that a coil is assigned individually to each key of the instrument, the fundamental frequency and therefore period of each of the expected notes is also a known constant.

Figure 7: Onset and amplitude detection.

With these assumptions made and referring to Figure 7, the onset detection works as follows. After a MIDI Note-On message is received in order to trigger a note, the microcontroller reads the velocity value, and uses it to reference a look-up table of pulse lengths. It then sends a pulse of that length to the MOSFET controlling the referenced solenoid. During the period of time that voltage is being applied to the solenoid coil, a short impulse of interference is present in the audio signal of nearby coils, as shown on the left of Figure 7 and noted in [10]. In order to prevent this impulse from interfering with the onset detection, the algorithm does not begin listening for onsets for an amount of time equal to the pulse applied, plus a 1.5 ms buffer.

When listening for the onset begins, a circular buffer maintains an averaged signal from which to make amplitude comparisons. With reference to this average, the algorithm then marks negative-going zero crossings in the audio stream. When three subsequent zero crossings have been observed that are each separated by the expected period of the played note, an onset is recorded as having taken place two periods earlier. The latency of the strike of that particular key, and at that particular velocity is then recorded as the time from the note being triggered to this onset time. If an onset has not been detected within 50 ms of the note being triggered, a time-out occurs and it is established that the solenoid did not make contact with the key. This approach to robotic percussion onset detection provides robust results from very soft to loud strikes and has low CPU overhead, making it suitable for low-power embedded systems.

4.3.2 Amplitude Detection

Each time the onset detector marks the first in a potential series of negative zero-crossings, the amplitude detector begins recording the audio input into a dedicated buffer. When three correctly spaced zero-crossings have occurred and the onset has been successfully detected, the amplitude

detector scans its buffer and records the minimum and maximum amplitudes of the buffer in relation to the averaged signal. The difference between these two points is recorded as the signal's amplitude.

4.3.3 Continuous Calibration

After a key is triggered and the MIR algorithms have recorded latency and amplitude values for a key at a certain pulse width, the continuous calibration routine is run. This routine plots the values among the other recorded values for the specific key, and conducts an interpolation between the new value and other nearest recorded values. This brings the current array of amplitudes more in line with the desired response graph which represents 126 equal steps in perceived loudness. It also creates a comprehensive record of the latency of each key, at each velocity. In the case that a time-out has occurred and the no-contact flag has been set, the algorithm simply adds 0.5 ms to the smallest pulse width at velocity value 1 and interpolates from that point.

Many modern digital sequencers provide a latency compensation feature to improve the timing of sequenced material. When latency compensation mode is enabled with a Program Change 70 message, the highest latency value of the instrument is returned via a MIDI CC message. If the sequencer's latency compensation is then set to this value, the instrument will use the information it has gathered about the latency of each velocity of each note to provide a uniform level of latency to every sequenced strike. It achieves this by playing softer hits with higher latency earlier and harder hits with lower latency later. As a result, the tightness of the timing of sequences is greatly improved, even in compositions with great dynamic variety.

This continuous calibration enables users to conduct performances with the instrument without lengthy manual calibration and without worrying that changing conditions during play will have a negative effect on the instrument's performance. If the instrument has just been installed in a new environment, a play-through of the intended composition during the sound-check will in most cases provide adequate opportunity for the instrument to automatically calibrate itself, but a thorough calibrate routine has also been included in the firmware and can be triggered by sending a MIDI program change message with a value of 60. This routine quickly triggers a sequence of notes that is designed to provide the instrument with maximum dynamic range, while making sure that interference between solenoids, coils and adjacent notes is avoided.

5. OTHER FEATURES

As a result of the closed-loop upgrades to the robotic glockenspiel, in addition to the improvements to the reliability, ease of use and dynamic range, several extra features are made possible by the additional hardware. The audio output from the instrument allows it to be amplified in performance contexts without the extra equipment, setup time and acoustic bleed and feedback problems inherent in using microphones. This also means that the audio feed can be routed through standard audio effects, or to a PC for creative digital signal processing. The extra performance information available to musical robots means that with creative programming, parameters of audio effects applied to the output signal can be perfectly synchronized with the sequence that is triggering the actuation of the keys. This new level of synchronization can provide many new creative possibilities and avenues for musical expression.

Another feature that this system adds to the instrument is the capability for the instrument itself to be used as a MIDI controller. By detecting onsets that were not caused

by the solenoids, the instrument can extract hit and velocity information and output MIDI Note commands. By processing the output MIDI signals externally it is possible to apply MIDI effects and processing and send them back to the instrument. This creates an interactive robotic instrument with use cases such as setting the instrument to physically perform echoes of a player's strikes, or to arpeggiate chords that are struck by a player in real-time.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper has presented the Closed-Loop Robotic Glockenspiel, a new robotic pitched-percussion instrument that brings musical robots a step closer towards the achieving the repeatability, reliability and usability of commercial electronic musical instruments. The embedded MIR system offers continuous calibration of the instrument that is invisible to the end user, and playing it is no more complicated than plugging in power and MIDI. The closed-loop system also adds new features to the instrument such as audio output via a standard 1/4" jack, and MIDI out functionality for interactive and computer synchronized performances.

Since this iteration of the Robotic Glockenspiel is still a proof of concept which uses prototyping microcontroller boards and changeable thru-hole circuit boards, implementing the final design on more compact and robust custom surface-mount circuitry with higher specifications will make the unit more serviceable and provide slightly higher performance. An in-depth analysis which precisely quantifies the improvements that this closed-loop configuration makes in a variety of areas is also planned. The next step will be to create a generalizable hardware and software framework to enable the addition of closed-loop embedded MIR to other existing musical robots, as well as streamlining the process of creating new robots with these features. In the future, these techniques can be applied to other categories of instrument such as string, wind, and unpitched percussion to provide continuous calibration of the tuning of pitches, timbres and other characteristics of performance whilst providing a number of new capabilities.

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